

Research

China-ASEAN Relation: The China's Strategic and Economic Interest in ASEAN

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Abstract: China with its enormous population and the gigantic emerging economy is the main driver behind the geopolitical reconfiguration that is taking place. ASEAN is one of the areas that is affected most directly by the rise of China. It is a key importance to China for access to critical energy and natural resources. The region is significant as a potential conduit for the promotion of China's diplomatic influence and for its strategic role as a vital crossroads of sea and land. China's main motivation for involvement in ASEAN is to further its national economic, political and strategic interests. In facing the challenges more efforts need to be made to build new trust and initiate new mutually beneficial actions. The BRI provides a new framework and opportunity for China and ASEAN to deepen their relations through close consultation and cooperation. China's rise, ASEAN's integration and the shift of the international center of gravity to the Asia-Pacific (or a wider Indo-Pacific) region will test the future of ASEAN-China relations. This paper aims to examine China and ASEAN relations in their proper perspective in economic, political security and military implications. China and ASEAN as neighbors are linked together by geography and interests.

Keywords: China-ASEAN Relations, Strategic Partner, Economic Interest, Geopolitics

Introduction

China and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) began their dialogue relations in July 1991, when the Malaysian government invited Qian Qichen, then the People Republic of China (PRC)'s Minister of Foreign Affairs, to attend the opening session of the 24th ASEAN Ministerial Meeting (AMM) in Kuala Lumpur. Subsequently, China was accorded full Dialogue

Partner status at the 29th AMM in July 1996 in Jakarta.¹ After attaining full Dialogue Partner status in 1996, ASEAN-China relations developed quickly. At the 7th ASEAN-China Summit in October 2003 in Bali, both sides agreed to sign the Joint Declaration of the Heads of State/Government on Strategic Partnership for Peace and Prosperity with Plans of Action (POA) to implement it. The current POA covers the period 2011-2015. The PRC is the first dialogue partner to accede to the Treaty of Amity and Cooperation (TAC) in 2003.² At the height of the 1997-1998 Asian financial crisis, China and ASEAN forged a closer relationship. The two sides subsequently launched a currency swap initiative and began negotiations on an ASEAN-China Free Trade Area (ACFTA), which entered into force in 2010.³ China and ASEAN have also collaborated to address transnational non-traditional security threats such as drug and human trafficking, piracy and terrorism. ASEAN and China have continued to enhance their political and security cooperation through regular dialogue and consultations, including the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF) and the East Asia Summit (EAS). Trade and economic ties between ASEAN and the PRC have been growing rapidly. China has been ASEAN's largest trading partner since 2009, while ASEAN is now China's third-largest trading partner.⁴

China's Rise and ASEAN

As a fastest and gigantic emerging power in East Asia, China with one fifth of the world population and its growing economy is the main driver behind the geopolitical reconfiguration that is taking place.⁵ ASEAN is a pillar of the postwar order in East Asia. Founded in 1967 by Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand, principally to coordinate security policy during the Cold War, the bloc was significantly enlarged in the 1990s, when it took in low-income countries Burma (Myanmar), Cambodia, Laos, and Vietnam. Southeast Asia is one of the areas that is affected most directly by the rise of China.⁶ It is also a key importance to China for access

¹ Chinvano, Anuson. 2015. "ASEAN-China Relations: Prospects and Challenges." *RJSH* (Thai Institute of Rangsit University) 2 (1): 9-14.

² Rustandi, Commodore Agus. 2016. "The South China Sea Dispute: Opportunities for ASEAN to enhance its policies in order to achieve resolution." *Indo-Pacific Strategic Papers* (The Centre for Defence and Strategic Studies (CDSS)).

³ Pomfret, Richard. 2017. *Economic Relations between China and ASEAN*. cpianalysis. September 13. Accessed August 10, 2019. <https://cpianalysis.org/2017/09/13/economic-relations-between-china-and-asean/>.

⁴ Vahalik, Bohdan. 2014. "Regional Bilateral Trade Analysis of the European Union, China and ASEAN." *Science Direct: Procedia Economics and Finance* (Elsevier Ltd.) 12 (2014): 709-717.

⁵ Renwick, Neil. 2016. *China as a Development Actor in Southeast Asia*. Institute of Development Studies, UK: Institute of Development Studies.

⁶ Yuan, Jing-dong. 2006. *China-ASEAN Relations: Perspectives, Prospectives and Implications for U.S. Interests*. Prod. US Government. Strategic Studies Institute, <http://www.StrategicStudiesInstitute.army.mil/>, October.

to critical energy and natural resources. The region is significant as a potential conduit for the promotion of China's diplomatic influence and for its strategic role as a vital crossroads of sea and land. The countries and peoples of Southeast Asia have traditionally formed an important part of China's trading, cultural and demographic outlook. China's main motivation for involvement in Southeast Asia is to further its national economic, political and strategic interests, each of which is important in its own right to Beijing's definition of its core national needs.⁷ The interaction between China and ASEAN will, to a great extent, affect the future and prospects of the entire Asian region. The economic, political security and military implications of China's rise are acutely felt in ASEAN.⁸ Since the mid-1990s, China and ASEAN have developed a growing partnership in security cooperation, economic/ trade interdependence, and the development and sharing of "Asian values".⁹ Compared to the late 1980s and early 1990s when Beijing had yet to establish or normalize diplomatic relations with key ASEAN member states and when the concerns over the "China threat" both drove Southeast Asia's armament and military buildup and were the major rationale for initiating a regional security arrangement to keep the United States engaged, the current state of China-ASEAN relationship is truly remarkable.¹⁰ While a China and Southeast Asia living in harmony contributes to regional peace, stability, and prosperity and minimizes the potential for conflicts over unresolved territorial disputes, the future direction of this relationship nevertheless could have major implications for long term U.S. interests in the region, especially if it evolves into a competitive and even exclusive regional trading bloc and a geo-strategic arrangement under the shadow of a growing and more assertive China.¹¹

China-ASEAN Economic Relations

China-ASEAN economic relations are both a major impetus and the most concrete indicator of their cooperation.¹² The normalization of relations between China and some ASEAN states in the 1970s coincided with a rise in Sino-ASEAN trade. The total volume of Sino-ASEAN trade was about US\$523 million in 1975, and grew to US\$2.064 billion in 1980 and US\$2.947 billion in

⁷ Rustandi, 2016. "The South China Sea Dispute: Opportunities for ASEAN to enhance its policies in order to achieve resolution." 4.

⁸ Alice, D. Ba. 2003. "China and ASEAN: Renavigating Relations for a 21st-Century Asia." *Asian Survey* (The Regents of the University of California) 43 (4): 622-647.

⁹ Chinivanno, 2015. "ASEAN-China Relations: Prospects and Challenges." 9-14.

¹⁰ Renwick, 2016. *China as a Development Actor in Southeast Asia*. 9.

¹¹ Yuan, 2006. *China-ASEAN Relations: Perspectives, Prospectives and Implications for U.S. Interests*. 6.

¹² Pejsova, Eva. 2016. *China's rise: the view from Singapore*. EUISS, European Union Institute for Security Studies (EUISS).

1984. By 1990, the value of Sino–ASEAN trade stood at US\$6.691 billion. By 1994, China’s trade with ASEAN had already increased more than 25 times over the volume in 1975. With admission of Vietnam (1995) and Myanmar and Laos (1997) to ASEAN the total volume of Sino–ASEAN trade increased to more than US\$19 billion.¹³ In November 2002, both sides signed the Framework Agreement on Comprehensive Economic Cooperation that established the ASEAN-China Free Trade Agreement (ACFTA) realized on 1 January 2010. The China-ASEAN Expo (CAEXPO) has been organized and hosted by China annually in Nanning since 2004 to showcase products from ASEAN and China.¹⁴ The ACFTA has a very large growth potential. It comprises a market of almost 2 billion people and USD 3 trillion in gross domestic product. Notably, bilateral trade relations between China and ASEAN are now reciprocal in that China is no longer the exporting competitor of past decades. It is now an important consumer market for ASEAN, which in turn is growing in importance to China’s manufacturing sector. Moreover, ASEAN is now China’s fourth-largest destination for outward investment and its third-largest source of foreign direct investment. Bilateral trade stood at USD 318.6 billion in 2012 and two-way investment is targeted to reach USD 150 billion by 2020.¹⁵ China has also established several mechanisms to support and strengthen further economic cooperation with ASEAN. In 2009, it established the USD 10 billion China-ASEAN Fund on Investment Cooperation and USD 15 billion in credit and preferential loans to support infrastructure development projects in ASEAN member states. Following the adoption of the Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity (MPAC) in 2010, China proposed to provide an additional USD 10 billion credit (USD 4 billion in preferential loans and 6 billion commercial loans) to support MPAC’s implementation. The increasingly important role of the Chinese (Ren Min Bi—RMB) as an international currency and the strengthening trade and investment relationships between China and the other South East Asian countries, this paper has investigated whether the RMB is in the process of replacing the US dollar as the anchor currency in nine ASEAN countries. The incorporating a break shows that the linkages between these currencies and the RMB and the US dollar respectively are equally important, and in fact in recent years the

¹³ Sanchita, Basu Das. 2017. "Southeast Asia Worries over Growing Economic Dependence on China." *Perspective* (ISEAS – YUSOF ISHAK Institute Analyse Current Events) 81 (2017).

¹⁴ Salidjanova, Nargiza, Koch-Weser Jacob, and Jason Klanderma. 2015. *China’s Economic Ties with ASEAN: A Country-by-Country Analysis*. U.S.-China Economic and Security Review Commission, Economic and Security Review Commission.

¹⁵ Pomfret, 2017. Economic Relations between China and ASEAN.

former have become stronger than the latter.¹⁶ Another China's economic interest in the Southeast Asia region is the important source of raw materials such as timber. Quite apart from illegal timber exports, the legitimate trade has been booming on the back of rising Chinese consumer demand. According to official Vietnamese statistics, wood exports totaled US\$5.37bn in 2013 – a 15.2 per cent increase from 2012. Over the past ten years, the Vietnamese wood industry has expanded rapidly, with an average export growth rate of 15.5 per cent every year.¹⁷ China's foreign direct investment (FDI) into ASEAN was almost US\$19bn in 2012. At the 16th ASEAN-China Summit on 9 October 2013, China took this a step further by presenting an initiative to set up an Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank to provide financial support to regional infrastructure projects, with priority on ASEAN connectivity. China also has become a major source of tourists for ASEAN. In 2012, almost 9 million Chinese tourists visited ASEAN countries, a growth rate of almost 20% over 2011. At the same time, almost 6 million tourists from ASEAN countries visited China in 2012.¹⁸ The ASEAN economies and China are increasingly getting tied to each other through economic diplomacy. This not only includes trade agreements but also economic cooperation project, like the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI).¹⁹

Geopolitical and Cultural Relations

China's political relations with its Southeast Asian neighbors have never been easy; commercial ties have been offset by territorial, ethnic and ideological disputes as well as occasional cross-border or maritime tensions.²⁰ China's present-day relations with some of the region's states date back to Zhou Enlai's bridge-building at the 1955 Bandung Conference (with Burma (Myanmar), Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, South Vietnam, Thailand, the Philippines, and the Democratic Republic of Vietnam). The Cold War's ideological competition and the first Indochina war split the region, its countries and peoples, while the Sino-Soviet dispute split the region's Communist parties.²¹ China's dramatic shifted to market socialism under Deng Xiaoping after 1979, and the country's subsequent transformation to a global economic powerhouse. This shift is reified in China's institutional involvement in ASEAN. Its diplomatic opening with ASEAN began in the

¹⁶ Caporalea, Guglielmo Maria. 2017. *Exchange rate linkages between the ASEAN currencies, the US dollar and the Chinese RMB*. Elsevier. July 03. Accessed August 10, 2019. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2017.07.091>.

¹⁷ Vahalik, 2014. "Regional Bilateral Trade Analysis of the European Union, China and ASEAN." 709-717.

¹⁸ Chinvarno, 2015. "ASEAN-China Relations: Prospects and Challenges." 10.

¹⁹ Sanchita, 2017. "Southeast Asia Worries over Growing Economic Dependence on China." 81.

²⁰ Sanchita, 2017. "Southeast Asia Worries over Growing Economic Dependence on China." 82.

²¹ Chinvarno, 2015. "ASEAN-China Relations: Prospects and Challenges." 11.

early 1990s, becoming a full Dialogue Partner in 1996. Today's relationship dates back to the signing of the ASEAN-China Strategic Partnership agreement in 2003. There are 11 agreed priority areas for cooperation: agriculture; information and communications technology (ICT); human resource development; Mekong Basin development; investment; energy; transport; culture; public health; tourism; and environment.²² Given the territorial disputes in the South China Sea, the flagship yet nonetheless impotent agreement is the Declaration on the Conduct of Parties in the South China Sea, signed in November 2002, with implementation guidelines eventually agreed in July 2011. Beyond the formalities, substantial tensions remain. For example, relations between China and the Philippines are still at their lowest point for decades, marked by the relative paucity of Beijing's humanitarian assistance in the wake of typhoon Haiyan and clashes in 2014 over disputed maritime waters. In addition, Sino-Vietnamese relations fell to a new low point in 2014, when the positioning of China's US\$1bn oil rig in contested waters close to the disputed Paracel Islands, accompanied by a flotilla of naval, coastguard and civilian ships, sparked bitter exchanges and led to anti-Chinese riots. Culturally, there is one significant factor in China's relationship with Southeast Asia – the ethnic Chinese diaspora and the discrimination, resentment, animosity and violence Chinese communities have experienced over the centuries. In socio-cultural fields, cooperation between ASEAN and China is very broad, covering education, culture, public health, science and technology, labor, local government and people-to-people exchanges, media, youth and social development. For example, on education, since 2010 ASEAN and China have made efforts to "Double 100,000 Goal of Student Mobility" that envisaged the number of exchange students from ASEAN countries to China to reach 100,000 by 2020 and vice versa. Ten ASEAN-China Education and Training Centers have been established in six Chinese provinces. ASEAN and China also designated the 2014 as ASEAN-China Cultural Exchange Year, and an ASEAN-China Centre has been established in Beijing as a one-stop information center promoting ASEAN-China cooperation in trade, investment, tourism, education and culture.²³

²² Chinvanno, 2015. "ASEAN-China Relations: Prospects and Challenges." 14.

²³ Loh, Stanley. 2017. *Taking Asean-China ties to the next level*. straitstimes. September 15. Accessed February 10, 2018. <http://www.straitstimes.com/opinion/taking-asean-china-ties-to-the-next-level>.

China-ASEAN Under the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)

China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which aims to fund and build infrastructure in more than 78 countries, is riding both high and low.²⁴ BRI brings opportunities in trade, engineering and in finance, particularly in supporting the internationalization of the Renminbi. But it also poses serious and fundamental challenges to the existing international legal framework, in relation to both commercial and political disputes. The BRI also impacts on foreign policy. Many Southeast Asian countries face the dilemma of being eager BRI participants and traditional US allies, unsure with which superpower to side on issues such as the South China Sea and international trade wars.²⁵ BRI is also known in one word as 'connectivity', but it is more than just the common one-dimensional view of connecting countries by hard infrastructure. With ASEAN countries, economies that are well-connected are those which have a high degree of exchange of both the inputs into economic activity and the outputs from economic activity. The connectivity between countries needs to be three-dimensional in order to deliver economic value for the local and international economy. These dimensions are, the cross border flow of goods and services, capital, and people. In the context of BRI, economies most active in all three dimensions of economic connectivity are likely to benefit the most from the initiative. China's supply chain connectivity has risen across BRI regions over the past decade, but ASEAN economies remain the most connected. This is likely to reflect a continuation of outsourcing to China from high-cost economies in the region, such as Singapore and Malaysia, while Chinese firms themselves outsource lower value-added processes to the region's cheapest economies such as Cambodia and Laos. Meanwhile, supply chain connectivity has also deepened across other BRI regions. Singapore, Vietnam, Thailand, Malaysia, Cambodia, and Myanmar are all ranked amongst the top ten most connected to China via trade, and China continues to deepen trading relations with partner economies in Southeast Asia. The Free Trade Agreement (FTA) with ASEAN was the first of its kind, between China and a regional organization, and was upgraded in 2014 as part of the BRI. Trade and investment flows have accelerated since this upgraded agreement came into effect in 2016. Geographical proximity to China has served ASEAN and other neighboring Asian Pacific countries well so far. Nonetheless, future success depends on the dynamism of policy targeted to

²⁴ Jie, Yu. 2018. "China and Southeast Asia: Many Belts and Roads to turn." In *China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and Southeast Asia*, by CIMB ASEAN Research Institute (CARI), 3. Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia: CIMB ASEAN Research Institute (CARI).

²⁵ Jie, 2018. "China and Southeast Asia: Many Belts and Roads to turn.", 3.

engage both the public and private sectors with all three dimensions of economic connectivity with China. The BRI needs to be a catalyst for regional and global growth, not an excuse for China to seek further leverage.²⁶

The South China Sea

China's claims in territorial and maritime during the 1990s stressed its disputes in the South China Sea with several ASEAN member states. The disputes involve complicated issues of overlapping maritime boundaries, territorial claims and sovereignty over the Paracel and the Spratly islands for which the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea offers no clear guidelines. Moreover, the South China Sea embraces some of the world's busiest sea lanes.²⁷ The South China Sea is also purported to be rich in petroleum, natural gas and other marine resources. The tension in the area in the 1990s, especially the clash between China and the Philippines over Mischief Reef in 1995, was mitigated somewhat by the *2002 Declaration on the Conduct of Parties in the South China Sea* (DOC). The conflicts intensified again with the U.S. "rebalancing" in the Asia-Pacific region. There is a perception in China that the U.S. actively supports some ASEAN countries against China. Consequently, China's renewed assertiveness over territorial and maritime disputes with ASEAN countries, particularly Vietnam and the Philippines, in the South China Sea since 2009 has only compounded the fears about China's growing military, especially naval, capabilities. China's increasing use of military and other law enforcement authorities to assert sovereignty in areas under dispute, as enclosed in its nine-dashed-lines map, is seen as a new element in the disputes. The apparent failure thus far of the regional multilateral diplomacy between ASEAN and China on this issue has raised the call for a binding code of conduct (COC) to mitigate the possibility of armed conflict. China has never been enthusiastic about a COC. While it had agreed in principle to discuss one with ASEAN in late 2011, it reversed its position in July 2012. However, it has been mentioned that not just China wants to go slow on drafting a COC because if one is finalized, all claimants will have to justify or retract from projects of strategic or economic interest to them.²⁸ This was made clear by the fact that ASEAN itself was unable to agree on the Guidelines for the Implementation of the DOC until 2011. This led to a call by ASEAN foreign ministers at

²⁶ Yan, Jinny. 2018. "The Belt and Road Initiative in Southeast Asia." In *China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and Southeast Asia*, by CARI, 4-7. Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia: CIMB ASEAN Research Institute (CARI).

²⁷ Sanchita, 2017. "Southeast Asia Worries over Growing Economic Dependence on China." 82.

²⁸ Caporalea, 2017. *Exchange rate linkages between the ASEAN currencies, the US dollar and the Chinese RMB*.

their annual meeting in Myanmar in August 2014 to hold “substantive” negotiations for an early conclusion of the COC. So the South China Sea lies at the crossroads of some of the most important trends in the Asia-Pacific region today: the rising power of China; the U.S. rebalancing toward Asia; and ASEAN’s increasing desire to shape the regional security environment and take the sharp edges off the growing competition between China and the United States.²⁹

Conclusion

Overall, China and ASEAN have done well in developing their cooperative relationship. Knowing ASEAN is always important to China’s grand strategy and China cherishes its relationship with ASEAN countries. China’s perspective on ASEAN has not been affected by the South China Sea disputes, even though they have had some negative effects on mutual trust and the environment for close cooperation. The economic, political security and military implications of China’s rise are acutely felt in ASEAN. It is impossible for ASEAN to ignore the rise of China as a potential hegemon in the region. As it has little power to restrain or confront China in case of a serious confrontation, the viable course of action for ASEAN is to accommodate and have a working relationship with China. In facing the challenges more efforts need to be made to build new trust and initiate new mutually beneficial actions. The BRI provides a new framework and opportunity for China and ASEAN to deepen their relations through close consultation and cooperation. China’s rise, ASEAN’s integration and the shift of the international center of gravity to the Asia-Pacific (or a wider Indo-Pacific) region will test the future of ASEAN-China relations. China and ASEAN as neighbors are linked together by geography and interests. For a better future, they need to frankly express their perspectives to each other and define their common goals and share their agendas in both bilateral and regional affairs.

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²⁹ Yuan, 2006. *China-ASEAN Relations: Perspectives, Prospectives and Implications for U.S. Interests*.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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